

Electron Spin Resonance Study of Pseudotetrahedral Copper(II) and Tetrahedral Cobalt(II) Complexes

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THE electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes¹ show two peaks at 13100 and 25000 cm^{-1} instead of only one peak below 10000 cm^{-1} (${}^2\text{T}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}$) which is characteristic of tetrahedral geometry. This was explained by the splitting of ground term ${}^3\text{T}_2$ into its low symmetry components in pseudotetrahedral configuration. The literature survey on esr studies of Cu^{II} complexes reveals a number of examples of complexes having distorted octahedral and square-planar geometries^{2,3} and only a few of them having pseudotetrahedral geometry^{4,5}. The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes¹ show one peak around 16000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^4\text{A}_1(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$ transition, characteristic of tetrahedral configuration. The esr study of Co^{II} octahedral and tetrahedral complexes is very scarce in the literature. Recently the unusual electronic and esr spectra of pseudotetrahedral complexes of Co^{II} with different amines have been reported⁶.

Therefore, it is of interest to study the esr spectra of pseudotetrahedral Cu^{II} and tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes. In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report in this note the esr study of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes with 2-methyl-3-aminoquinazoline-4-one (MAQ) and 2-phenyl-3-aminoquinazoline-4-one (PAQ).

Experimental

The ligands were prepared as reported earlier⁷. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc and melting point determination. The Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes were prepared using metal sulphate and metal acetate, respectively. In the preparation of all the complexes the following general procedure was adopted. Metal salt was dissolved in methanol. Methanolic ligand solution in slight excess over the 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) ratio was added to it dropwise with constant stirring. The complex was formed immediately after refluxing the reaction mixture for 30 min on water bath. It was filtered, washed several times with hot water and then with methanol until free from the reagent. The complex was dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. The analytical data (C, H and N) for the ligands and their complexes were obtained from Micro-analytical Laboratory, University of Calcutta. The metal content in the complexes was determined using the standard procedures. The esr spectra of the solid complexes were recorded at room temperature using Varian E-4 X-band spectrophotometer. Typical spectra of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes are given in

Figs. 1 and 2. Spin Hamiltonian parameters like g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} have been calculated from the spectra applying the method of Kneubuhl⁸. These along with the other parameters evaluated are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Esr spectrum of Cu^{II} -MPQ.

Fig. 2. Esr spectrum of Co^{II} -MPQ.

TABLE 1—ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Parameter	[Cu MAQ $\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$]	[Cu PAQ $\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$]	[CoMAQ $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$]	[Co PAQ $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$]
g_{\parallel}	2.29	2.28	—	—
g_{\perp}	2.06	2.07	—	—
g_{av}	2.14	2.14	2.63	2.59
$A_{\parallel}(\text{cm}^{-1})$	5.3×10^{-4}	4.9×10^{-4}	—	—
$A_{\perp}(\text{cm}^{-1})$	2.5×10^{-4}	2.3×10^{-4}	—	—
$A_{\text{av}}(\text{cm}^{-1})$	3.43×10^{-4}	3.17×10^{-4}	—	—
G	4.99	4.10	—	—
K_{\perp}^{\parallel}	0.57	0.55	—	—
K_{\parallel}^{\perp}	0.30	0.35	—	—
$-\lambda_0(\text{cm}^{-1})$	828	828	—	—
$-\lambda(\text{cm}^{-1})$	471	454	—	—

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (C, H, N and metal) of the complexes indicate that their composition can

be represented as $[\text{CuLSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{CoL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$, where $\text{L} = \text{MAQ}$ or PAQ .

Cu^{II} ion having d^9 configuration can form complexes of octahedral, square-planar and tetrahedral geometries. Because of the Jahn-Teller effect the distortion occurs from the regular geometries in Cu^{II} complexes. The distortion depends on the presence of unpaired electron in different orbitals. In an elongated octahedron the unpaired electron lies in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital whereas in compressed octahedron it lies in d_{z^2} orbital. In a pseudotetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes the unpaired electron lies in d_{xy} orbital. On the basis of g tensor values, Singh concluded that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ in an elongated octahedron, whereas $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp}$ in compressed form⁹. Sharnoff observed that $g_{\perp} < g_{\parallel}$ in pseudotetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes¹⁰.

The esr spectra of Cu^{II} complexes of MAQ and PAQ exhibit a set of four hyperfine lines, which result from the coupling of ^{63}Cu nucleus ($I = 3/2$) with the unpaired electron. Cu^{II} complexes with tetrahedral geometry, where the ground term is essentially 3T_2 , show two characteristic properties: (i) their esr signals are observed only at very low temperature and (ii) the g values are very widely different from 2.0023. This is because the three states of T_2 , close in energy, are connected by the spin-orbital operator. The present Cu^{II} complexes, on the other hand, show esr signals at room temperature and also the g values are not far from 2.0023 (Table 1). This suggests that the ground term is not essentially 3T_2 and that some of its orbital degeneracy is lifted by the low symmetry component of the ligand field. This supports the observation made earlier from the electronic spectra of these complexes¹. From Table 1, it can be seen that the g_{\parallel} obtained for the complexes is less than 2.3 indicating covalent character of the metal-ligand bond². The axial symmetry parameter G , defined as $g_{\parallel} - 2.0023/g_{\perp} - 2.0023$, is found to be greater than 4, suggesting that there is no interaction between copper centres in the solid state¹¹. Further, orbital reduction parameters have been calculated¹² and the values of K_{\parallel}^2 are greater than those of K_{\perp}^2 , indicating that the complexes are of out-of-plane- π -bonded type. Spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) for the complexes is less than that of the free metal ion (λ_0) suggesting mixing of ground and excited terms.

The esr study of octahedral and tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes is of large interest. The 4F state of Co^{II} in an octahedral field is split into three states with $^4T_{2g}$ state lowest in energy. Since these states are connected by the spin-orbit coupling, the spin-lattice relaxation times are short, making esr measurements possible only at low temperatures. But in tetrahedral field, 4F state of the d^7 system has the orbital singlet state (4A_1), lowest in energy and with all excited states being at much higher energies. This situation gives rise to relatively large spin-lattice relaxation times and gives narrow esr absorption lines even at room temperature¹². But in contrast, the resolution of esr spectra of the present Co^{II}

complexes at room temperature is poor due to which different g and A values could not be obtained. However, from the single broad band observed, g_{av} has been calculated (Table 1).

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Studies on Copper(II) Mixed β -Diketonates and Their Adducts with Nitrogen Bases

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THE chemistry of metal β -diketonates has aroused much recent interest in such diverse areas¹ as spectral studies, gas chromatography, solvent extractions, column and thin layer chromatography, nmr shift reagents, laser technology and as initiators in free radical polymerisation². The quasi-aromatic character of such compounds have also received considerable attention. The formation of adducts of metal β -diketone chelates plays an important role in the synergistic enhancement of the solvent extraction of metal ions³. Several base adducts of zinc(II) and copper(II) β -diketonates were previously reported by us⁴⁻⁸. As a part of the general programme on studies on the linkage modes of β -diketonates in transition metal complexes the lability of the